

The Influence of Product Innovation and Customer Satisfaction Level on Repurchase Intention: A Study on the Markikas Kitchen Catering Culinary Business in Makassar City

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to determine the effect of product innovation on repurchase intention mediated by customer satisfaction at Catering Markikas Kitchen. The study uses a descriptive quantitative method (Path Analysis) and uses Smart-PLS as a test tool. In the research sample through probability sampling techniques, simple random sampling of a population of 298 and a sample of 100 respondents who are classified as Catering Markikas Kitchen customers. The results of the direct effect analysis show that product innovation has a positive and significant effect on repurchase intention and customer satisfaction. In addition, the results of the indirect effect analysis show that product innovation has a positive and significant effect on repurchase intention through customer satisfaction. Suggestions that can be given to Catering Markikas Kitchen business owners are to continue to innovate but still maintain the taste and quality of the product. However, other factors must be considered to continue to support customer satisfaction and create repurchase intention.

KEYWORDS: Culinary business, customer satisfaction, product innovation, repurchase intention

A. INTRODUCTION

The impact of the creative sector on the diverse social and cultural landscape of Burkinabe and Indonesian society is a motivation for the growth of Indonesia's creative industry (Rakib, 2017). The food and beverage industry is a major attraction that should not be ignored. Various types of businesses operate in this sector, including restaurants, coffee shops, and catering companies. Food is very important, especially in facilitating the organization of events (Macca et al., 2024). The Ministry of Industry stated that the contribution of this sector is evident in its consistent and important role in the GDP of the non-oil and gas industry 3. In the third quarter of 2020, the food and beverage sector was recognized as the largest contributor to national GDP with a share of 7.02% (Laras Saraswati et al., 2022). As a result, South Sulawesi is again ranked at the top of the food and beverage supply industry in 2023 with a total of 95.05 thousand people. Products represent valuable entities that are positioned in the market landscape to respond to consumer needs and aspirations. Creativity increases the company's survival and also outperforms competitors. Consumers who remain loyal to a product will find it difficult to switch to alternatives unless they feel that the product fails to meet their expectations (Laras Saraswati et al., 2022). The goal of repurchasing can be achieved by building and maintaining strong relationships through continuous improvement of customer benefits and satisfaction. Customer satisfaction represents an essential strategic dimension in business sustainability, because it has the potential to be a major determinant in forming purchasing decision tendencies in the future (Lina, 2022).

Food must also have the ability to standardize quality products to assess product quality based on market demand. Naturally, the standards set must include guidelines for quality products to ensure overall product excellence (Dermawan, 2022). Impact on Local-based economic development supported by the existence of novelty and innovation both in terms of products and services that always encourage people to visit, see, know, feel and even want to buy the products or services traded (Rakib et al., 2018). In the dynamics of the increasingly progressive growth of the culinary industry, strategic adaptability is a necessity for business entities to maintain relevance and competitiveness in the midst of an ever-evolving market landscape. Product innovation plays an important role in maintaining a unique position in an ever-competitive market.

Technological advances have facilitated the accessibility of the majority of the population to providers of basic necessities through online platforms. The presence of online stores opens up space for consumers to navigate a variety of commercial alternatives that are in line with personal preferences and orientations of each individual's choices (Rakib, Arifah, et al., 2023). More and more

food businesses, especially catering companies, are struggling to stay operational for a long period of time. Many of these companies face difficulties or bankruptcy for several reasons, including poor management of the including poor management, the absence of a marketing plan, lack of innovation in product offerings, and also poor product quality in terms of taste or service, which causes customer doubts due to unmet expectations. In marketing, converting consumers into customers is a challenge (Olsson et al., 2021).

Objective

In this study, it will be analyzed how product innovation influences repurchase intention through customer satisfaction. This research is important to be conducted in Makassar City because Makassar City in the catering service business has quite tight competition, so that later this research can help.

B. LITERATUR REVIEW

1. Entrepreneurship

The role of entrepreneurship as one of the best solutions in various challenges of social development. Entrepreneurship that contains economically productive activities to facilitate transactions and interactions that are equal and mutually beneficial (Rakib, 2016). Entrepreneurship is a process and innovation carried out by individuals or groups in identifying opportunities, designing, and managing a business with the aim of creating added value in the form of products or services, and daring to take calculated risks in order to achieve business success, which ultimately not only has an impact on increasing personal income, but also has the potential to contribute to the acceleration of economic growth and expansion of employment opportunities in the social order of society. Entrepreneurs are expected to be able to develop creative, innovative thinking, and have the ability to face challenges and limitations, such as limited capital, time, or networks, so that they can build a sustainable entrepreneurial ecosystem in the surrounding environment and the wider community. Characteristics of entrepreneurial attitudes include being innovative, daring to take risks, proactive, disciplined, highly committed, honest, creative, independent, realistic, diligent, punctual, friendly, polite, cheerful, sociable, flexible, helpful, serious, responsible, and have a sense of ownership of the Company (Syamsidar, Muhammad Rakib, 2019).

2. Catering

Catering is also referred to as field service for ready-to-eat food, which, upon request, is brought directly to the location of the order. Catering is often needed for events such as weddings, seminars, religious gatherings, birthdays, and others (Shaikh et al., 2019). Catering businesses usually have a group of chefs and support staff who are dedicated to ensuring that the food is delicious and of high quality, as well as being cleaned and customized to customer preferences. Typically, food preparation is done in the employer's kitchen, after which the food is transported to the event location or wherever the consumer requires it. Modern society shows high mobility and active businesses, so the demand for catering services is increasing, which is considered to offer a practical solution for food consumption without having to cook for yourself. As a result, this sector has emerged as a promising business opportunity today. Today, the catering business offers great opportunities for expansion, creating opportunities for individuals with sufficient skills and financial resources. Rapid technological advances allow companies to use the platform for advertising purposes. The Internet, a means of communication and information, is well known in the municipality for offering an optimal and most adaptable usage environment.

3. Product Innovation

Product creativity is an effort by economic actors to improve, perfect, create, and advance products that are currently being produced. Innovation can result from elements such as customer input or feedback and new discoveries (Herman et al., 2018). Organizations can use technology innovatively, create information and products, promote new offerings. The emergence of product innovation is primarily aimed at meeting market needs, allowing businesses to leverage it as a competitive advantage. Product innovation represents a strategic entity that not only provides functional impacts on optimizing corporate performance, but also acts as a mediating mechanism that affirms the relationship between market sensitivity and organizational capabilities in achieving operational effectiveness (Rosyihuddin et al., 2022). Product creativity in entrepreneurship involves not only inventing something completely new but also making design changes, useful improvements, attractive modifications, or even more attractive packaging, all with the aim of to improve customer satisfaction and increase market share. For entrepreneurs, product innovation is critical, as

the market becomes more dynamic and competitive, with consumers becoming more knowledgeable and internalizing high expectations for the attributes and performance of the products they consume. As a result, entrepreneurs must consistently react to changing trends, technologies, and consumer preferences by conducting comprehensive market research, leveraging the latest technology, embracing creativity, and collaborating as a team, all while avoiding a decline in sales, even if they cannot match more advanced competitors. Therefore, the capacity to continuously produce new products is a key element for the continued success and sustainability of the company.

4. Customer Satisfaction

Satisfaction refers to how aware a person is after assessing the results of his performance or seeing his understanding of his expectations. The perception of customer satisfaction can create a guarantee that customers will comply with the decision to repurchase if they already trust a particular product or service (Prianggoro & Sitio, 2020). Ultimately, generating customer satisfaction means providing a competitive advantage to the company, which involves aligning the relationship between the business and its clients, building a solid foundation or ensuring customer satisfaction, and generating constructive feedback for the company. To engage customers who want to buy or take advantage of the company's offerings, providing after-sales service is essential (Kurniawan & Silitonga, 2024). For entrepreneurs, increasing and maintaining customer satisfaction requires a thorough understanding of consumer preferences and needs through extensive market research, offering attentive and friendly service, ensuring consistent product quality, and embracing innovations that align with emerging market trends and demands. Site selection must be strategic, considering accessibility, efficiency, and attractiveness to drive business success and prevent potential losses. For culinary entrepreneurs, choosing a business location is not just about geography, but also a marketing strategy that affects the success and sustainability of the business.

5. Repurchase Intention

The motivation behind the act of repurchasing reflects a repetitive pattern of consumer behavior within a certain temporal framework, the construction of which is influenced by the accumulation of consumer interactional experiences with previous products or services. This is questionable because there is a satisfaction factor that greatly influences repurchase intentions (Chatzoglou et al., 2022). Repurchase motives serve as significant indicators to predict consumption behavior; if consumers show good intentions to repurchase, it reflects commitment to the brand, indicating that the brand is viewed positively (Rakib, Azis, et al., 2023). Repurchase intention is the motivation of customers to acquire a particular product or service after they are satisfied with the product or service. Repurchase intention is a psychological and behavioral state in which, after an initial purchase experience, consumers express a desire or urge to acquire a product or service from the same brand, often stemming from significant customer satisfaction with the quality of the product or service. Perceptions of service and value are recognized through recent transactions. Repurchase targets are an important indicator of customer loyalty and will be an important factor for business success in terms of customer loyalty amidst intense competition and dynamics market. When customers are happy and confident that the brand matches their preferences, consumers may repurchase the same product or expand consumption by exploring product lines within the brand.

C. METHODOLOGY

The research method used in this study is adjusted to the research framework and the variables studied. The approach used in this study involves the quantitative methods outlined and the evaluation of the hypotheses put forward in this study. Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) serves as an analysis technique, intended to test the relationship between variables included in the model. This study uses a population sampling method and uses a structured questionnaire for data collection.

Variables play an important role in research. Variables are properties, concepts, or values that can be changed or assessed in research. Therefore, this study includes three variables, namely product innovation as an independent variable, customer satisfaction as a mediating variable, and repurchase intention as a dependent variable.

In this study, the operational definition is a specific and measurable description or explanation of how a variable will be studied. Product innovation has 3 indicators of design change, technical innovation and product development. Customer satisfaction has 5 indicators of loyalty, creating (WOM), meeting expectations, service quality, and location. Repurchase intention has 3 indicators of transactional intention, referential intention and explorative intention.

In this research population, there were 298 consumers who made purchases at Catering Markikas Kitchen for 6 months in July - December. And the sample of this study consisted of 100 customers obtained using the Slovin formula and those included in the characteristics were purchases of at least 2x for 6 months at Catering Markikas Kitchen and respondents who could be contacted via social media.

The data acquisition strategy implemented includes a direct observational approach on site at the Markikas Kitchen Catering business. And using a questionnaire to collect data from consumers regarding their experiences in consuming its products or services. In filling out this questionnaire using a Likert scale, namely a scale of 1-5. Value 1 for an assessment of strongly disagree (STS), Value 2 for an assessment of disagree (TS), Value 3 for an assessment of less agree (KS), Value 4 for an assessment of agree (S), Value 5 for an assessment of strongly agree (SS). In this study, a number of hypotheses are formulated as initial formulations that represent theoretical assumptions about research problems, the validity of which needs to be verified through empirical testing. The hypotheses describe the relational construction that is the focus of exploration in the analytical framework, namely:

- H1: Product innovation influences repurchase intention in the culinary business.
- H2: Product innovation has an effect on customer satisfaction in the culinary business.
- H3: Customer satisfaction influences repurchase intention in the culinary business.
- H4: Product innovation influences repurchase intention through customer satisfaction in the culinary business.

D. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Result

Respondent Characteristics Results

There are three characteristics included in this study, namely gender, age, and education level of respondents with 100 selected respondents. Gender Characteristics that out of 100 Markikas Kitchen customers who became respondents, there were 37 people male. While the total number of female respondents is 63 people who are dominant in the characteristics of this study. In the age characteristics that have been determined, the age interval of 18-25 years is 40 people, in the interval of 26-35 years there are 44 people who are dominant in this study, and in the interval > 35 years there are 16 people. Characteristics at the last level of education of high school / vocational high school or equivalent are 41 people, S1 level is 57 people and S2 is 2 people.

Data Analysis

1. Outer model Analysis

In this research result to measure the validity and reliability of the model. Testing of the measurement model is used to determine the specification of the relationship between latent variables and their indicators, thus including testing convergent validity, discriminant validity, and reliability.

- a. Convergent validity, of each item shows a loading factor value of > 0.7 if there is an item < 0.7 then the item is eliminated from the model (Nasution et al., 2020). The indicators used in this study have conceptual feasibility in measuring the intended construct, and are able to represent data accurately according to the variables studied.
- b.
- c. Construct Reliability and Validity Test

Table 1. Construct Reliability and Validity Test Results

Variable	Cronbach alpha	Composite reliability (ρ_a)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
Product Innovation	0.928	0.931	0.581
Customer Satisfaction	0.960	0.961	0.643
Repurchase Intention	0.972	0.974	0.682

Source: Data processing results, 2025

Based on Table 1, the data can be said to be reliable, several requirements are needed such as Cronbach's alpha value > 0.7 , ρ_a value > 0.7 , and AVE > 0.5 (Cheung et al., 2024). The values generated in the data above have met the requirements, so they can be said to be reliable.

d. Discriminant Validity Test

Table 2. Cross Loading Test Results

Variable	Product Innovation	Repurchase Intention	Customer Satisfaction
PI1	0.760	0.406	0.581
PI2	0.798	0.530	0.664
PI3	0.777	0.560	0.666
PI4	0.766	0.558	0.641
PI5	0.765	0.463	0.579
PI6	0.742	0.518	0.573
PI7	0.763	0.437	0.488
PI8	0.772	0.387	0.471
PI9	0.741	0.496	0.585
PI10	0.726	0.448	0.466
PI11	0.774	0.463	0.664
RI1	0.534	0.790	0.666
RI2	0.508	0.831	0.456
RI3	0.519	0.836	0.458
RI4	0.473	0.846	0.558
RI5	0.518	0.827	0.486
RI6	0.498	0.828	0.497
RI7	0.491	0.896	0.506
RI8	0.453	0.799	0.508
RI9	0.558	0.848	0.564
RI10	0.548	0.855	0.555
RI11	0.590	0.846	0.569
RI12	0.593	0.834	0.599
RI13	0.509	0.878	0.545
RI14	0.500	0.822	0.497
RI15	0.425	0.826	0.438
RI16	0.622	0.789	0.717
RI17	0.475	0.732	0.521
RI18	0.535	0.770	0.610
CS1	0.594	0.550	0.742
CS2	0.611	0.530	0.775
CS3	0.648	0.600	0.825
CS4	0.635	0.522	0.808
CS5	0.689	0.544	0.807
CS6	0.596	0.549	0.794
CS7	0.600	0.472	0.808
CS8	0.563	0.430	0.810
CS9	0.656	0.511	0.830
CS10	0.557	0.584	0.779
CS11	0.516	0.520	0.787
CS12	0.497	0.472	0.813
CS13	0.679	0.505	0.810
CS14	0.571	0.445	0.800
CS15	0.660	0.558	0.832

Source: Data processing results, 2025

Evaluation of the cross loadings of each construct is carried out to confirm that the strongest relationship of measurement items is in the original construct compared to other constructs. Analytical preferences determine the ideal cross loading value to be above the threshold of 0.70 (Nasution et al., 2020). The values found above are > 0.7 and between constructs and their measurement items are greater, so they are acceptable.

Table 3. Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT)

Variable	Mark
RI <-> PI	0.655
CS <-> PI	0.790
CS <-> RI	0.662

Source: Data processing results, 2025

Based on Table 3, the Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT) value should ideally be below the threshold of 0.90 to ensure the achievement of discriminant validity between reflective constructs. If the HTMT value is.

2. Inner Model Analysis

The inner model or structural model represents an estimative network between latent constructs formulated from a theoretical basis. This model functions as a predictive framework for the causal relationships that are intertwined between latent entities in the conceptual structure (Aburumman et al., 2023).

Table 4. R-Square Value

Variable	R-Square
Repurchase Intention	0.471
Customer Satisfaction	0.576

Source: Data processing results, 2025

R-Square analysis is used to identify the proportion of exogenous variable contribution in forming the variability of endogenous constructs. Referring to Table 4, the R-Square value of 0.471 on the Repurchase Intention construct indicates that 47.1% of the dynamics of the construct are explained simultaneously by product innovation and customer satisfaction, while the remaining 52.9% comes from the influence of external entities outside the scope of the model. The customer satisfaction construct shows an R-Square value of 0.576, indicating that 57.6% of the variation of this construct is influenced by product innovation, while the remaining 42.4% reflects the intervention of other exogenous factors that are not accommodated in the structure of the model built.

Thus, this variable indicates that the model used has representative capabilities in explaining the relational dynamics between product innovation, repurchase intention, and customer satisfaction. Although in the moderate category, the level of adequacy still shows the influence of significant factors in the model structure.

Table 5. F-Square

Variable Relationship	F-Square	Information
PI > RI	0.088	Little influence
PI > CS	1.359	Big influence
CS > RI	0.128	Little influence

Source: Data processing results, 2025

Based on Table 5, this test is conducted to analyze the level of influence of latent variables whether they are weak, moderate, or strong at the structural model level. Based on the results of data processing in Table 5, the influence of Product Innovation (X) on Repurchase Intention (Y) has an effect size of 0.088 which is classified as a small influence but is approaching a moderate influence, while the Product Innovation variable (X) on Customer Satisfaction (Z) has an effect size of 1.359 which is classified as

a large influence, and the Customer Satisfaction variable (Z) on Repurchase Intention (Y) has an effect size of 0.128 which is included in the interpretation that tends to approach a moderate influence, but can still be categorized as a small but significant influence.

Hypothesis Testing

Figure 1 Research model results
 Source: Data processing results, 2025

Based on Figure 1, the hypothesis testing process is carried out to assess the significance of the relationship between variables in the model. A relationship is declared significant if it meets the criteria of t-statistic > 1.96 or pvalue < 0.05; conversely, the hypothesis will be rejected if it does not reach the acceptance threshold. This evaluation is based on the output path coefficients and specific effects which act as an inferential basis in testing structural hypotheses (Setia et al., 2024).

Table 6. Direct Effect Test

Variable	Original (O)	Sample (M)	Mean	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
PI > RI	0.332	0.336		0.127	2.607	0.009
PI > CS	0.759	0.760		0.061	12.401	0.000
CS > RI	0.399	0.391		0.139	2.877	0.004

Source: Data processing results, 2025

As reflected in Table 6, the direct effect analysis aims to test the hypothesis regarding the direct causal relationship between the independent and dependent variables through the measurement of the path coefficient. Based on Table 6, all variables show a t-statistic value > 1.96 and a p-value < 0.05, which indicates that the significance criteria have been met, so that the hypothesis

regarding the direct effect can be accepted empirically. The relationship between product innovation and repurchase intention is proven significant with a t-statistic of 2.641 (> 1.96) and a p-value of 0.009 (< 0.05). Likewise, the effect of product innovation on customer satisfaction is strengthened by a t-statistic of 12.401 and a p-value of 0.000, both of which meet the significance threshold. Furthermore, the relationship between customer satisfaction and repurchase intention is also confirmed through a t-statistic of 2.877 and a p-value of 0.004, each of which is within the range of values that justify the acceptance of the hypothesis.

Table 7. Indirect Effect Test (Mediation Influence)

Variable	Original (O)	Sample (M)	Sample Mean	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics ((O/STEDV))	P Values
PI – CS – RI CZ	0.303	0.298		0.109	2.779	0.005

Source: Data processing results, 2025

Based on Table 7, the hypothesis that product innovation has an effect on repurchase intention through customer satisfaction is proven, as can be seen from the results of the coefficient value of the indirect influence path which has an original sample value of 0.303, a sample mean of 0.298, and a standard deviation of 0.109. The t-statistic value is 2.779 and the p-value is 0.005. This means that product innovation has a positive effect on repurchase intention through customer satisfaction because it has passed the hypothesis test criteria.

Discussion

The Influence of Product Innovation on Repurchase Intention

Product innovation shows a direct positive influence on repurchase intention in the culinary service entity Markikas Kitchen, as reflected in the path coefficient value of 0.332 with a t-statistic of 2.607 (> 1.96) and a p-value of 0.009 (< 0.05), which statistically indicates the significance of the relationship. This finding reflects that the higher the quality of product innovation presented, the greater the tendency of customers, both loyal and potential new users, to make repeat purchases of the services offered.

With this study, it was found that the existence of product innovation or creative ideas from Markikas Kitchen proved that there was a significant influence on acceptable repurchase intentions. So it can be concluded that product innovation also plays an important role in increasing customer repurchase intentions in food catering businesses, because by presenting new menu variations, continuously improved taste quality, and attractive presentation, customers feel more satisfied and interested in using the service again and want to try new things. However, product innovation does not necessarily become an important point in making customers loyal, because many things are influenced by customer perceptions such as service quality, price, taste, brand image, product quality, and customer experience which together influence repurchase decisions, therefore the direct influence can be seen as small but still positive and significant because there are several other dominant influences.

The findings of this study are consistent with the results of the study (Kurniawan & Silitonga, 2024), which identified a significant influence between product innovation and consumer purchasing interest. The consistency of the findings is also reflected in the study (Surya Negara et al., 2021), which shows that product innovation makes a positive and significant contribution to repurchase interest in food products in the city of Blitar. In line with (Gitaringga et al., 2024) also confirms that product innovation has a positive and significant influence on repurchase intention.

The Influence of Product Innovation on Customer Satisfaction

The empirical findings in this study indicate that product innovation contributes significantly and positively to the formation of customer satisfaction at Markikas Kitchen, as reflected in the path coefficient value of 0.759, t-statistic 12.401 (> 1.96), and p-value 0.000 (< 0.05). Thus, the causal relationship between the two constructs can be statistically accepted within the framework of the model built. The implications of this finding indicate that the variety of innovations implemented by Markikas Kitchen are able to form a positive perception in the minds of customers regarding the quality of products and services provided. Thus, the level of customer satisfaction functions as a reflection of the quality of service as well as the image built by the business entity. Because the diversity of product innovations offered is able to create a positive experience for customers, and make customers

not easily bored with monotonous or just that menu, while also strengthening customer loyalty and satisfaction with Markikas Kitchen. Like one of the innovations issued by Markikas Kitchen, namely the tumpeng menu in the form of a miniature building, the first in Makassar City. With this, it can be said that companies or business actors who consistently innovate products will be better able to build customer loyalty and maintain their competitive position in the market.

The findings in this study are in line with the study of (Fadillah et al., 2022) which has a positive and significant influence on customer satisfaction. The conformity of the results was also found in the study (Ayodele & Oluwayemi, 2019), which identified a positive and significant relationship between product innovation and customer satisfaction at Kuswini Catering. The consistency of the findings is also strengthened by the study (Winarti et al., 2021), which underlines a similar contribution in the context of customer satisfaction. However, it is not in line with the study (Al Sukri et al., 2022) which states that product innovation does not have a significant effect on customer satisfaction.

The Influence of Customer Satisfaction on Repurchase Intention

The results of this research analysis were obtained by researchers that customer satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on repurchase intention at Markikas Kitchen with the magnitude of the influence of the path coefficient value of 0.399, the t-statistics value of $2.877 > 1.96$, and the p-values of 0.004 Kitchen. The sense of satisfaction given by customers marked by joy and satisfaction encourages customers to return to Catering Markikas Kitchen to enjoy its products which then influences the increase in repurchase intentions. It can be concluded that the intensity of satisfaction experienced by customers towards the products or services received contributes proportionally to the increase in the tendency of repurchase behavior in the future. Customer satisfaction not only acts as the main indicator in building loyalty but also becomes a key factor that drives repurchase decisions, so the Company needs to continue to improve its products both in terms of innovation and service in order to maintain and strengthen long-term relationships with customers and achieve sustainable business success. Thus, when the company aims to encourage customers to make repeat purchases, the company should not only focus on promotion as the main factor, but also strive to increase customer commitment and positive perceptions of the company.

The findings in this study are consistent with the results of the study by (Ellitan et al., 2023) which showed a positive and significant influence between customer satisfaction and repurchase intention. This consistency is also reflected in the studies (Tufahati et al., 2021) and (Hidayat et al., 2020) which both confirmed a positive and significant relationship between the two variables.

The Influence of Product Innovation on Repurchase Intention Through Customer Satisfaction.

Based on the results of the analysis, it was found that customer satisfaction positively and significantly mediates the relationship between product innovation and repurchase intention at Markikas Kitchen. This is indicated by the path coefficient value of 0.303, t-statistic 2.779 (> 1.96), and p-value 0.005 (< 0.05), which indicates that the mediation path is statistically accepted. This finding suggests that the perception of satisfaction formed in the minds of customers contributes to strengthening the impact of product innovation on the tendency to make repeat purchases. In this context, customers tend to evaluate product innovation objectively, and the resulting level of satisfaction, whether high or low, has a significant influence on the intensity of repeat purchases of the services provided by Markikas Kitchen.

This study identifies that the presence of customer satisfaction as a mediating variable validates the existence of a significant influence between product innovation and repurchase intention, which is empirically acceptable. The higher the perception of the quality of innovation that is able to meet or even exceed consumer expectations, the level of satisfaction formed also increases proportionally. This satisfaction then plays a key role in consolidating the consumer's internal drive to make repeat purchases in the future.

The findings in this study are in line with the study (Ellitan et al., 2023) which shows that consumer satisfaction acts as a mediating variable in strengthening the positive relationship between product innovation and repurchase intention. The conformity of the results is also reflected in the study (Ebrahimi & Tootoonkavan, 2014) which indicates that consumer satisfaction has the capability to significantly mediate the influence of product innovation on repurchase intention.

E. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Product innovation has a positive and significant effect on repurchase intention at Catering Markikas Kitchen. That the existence of innovation or new ideas issued can increase repurchase in the business. However, product innovation does not

necessarily become one of the things that makes customers loyal but many things can influence it. Product innovation has a positive and significant impact on customer satisfaction at Markikas Kitchen by creating new and unique things while still following needs or trends, and maintaining the taste and quality of the product which makes customers satisfied with their expectations. Customer satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on repurchase intention at Markikas Kitchen. The creation of customer satisfaction then has a tendency to make repeat purchases in the future, either trying new products or the same product and also become one of the key factors that drive repeat purchase decisions. Customer satisfaction that mediates the relationship between product innovation and repurchase intention has a positive and significant effect on Markikas Kitchen. Customer satisfaction is created so that it can be a mediation between product innovation while maintaining quality and customer needs, thereby strengthening customer desire to make repeat purchases.

As a manufacturer, it is advisable to continue to innovate and think of new and creative ideas that are different from other competitors, but still maintain quality and adjust to customer tastes. Consistent innovation will not only increase customer satisfaction through a more interesting dining experience but also encourage customer repurchase intentions. And continue to look at other factors besides product innovation to continue to support consumer satisfaction and create repurchase intentions

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